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Work Life Balance: A Case Study of Working Women in Public Sector Organization

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Abstract

Despite of a large amount of empirical evidences on western culture, very small amount of research has focused the experience of working women in the context of Pakistan. In labor market of Pakistan, gender inequalities are very prominent and women are usually force towards some predefined professions where they have to put some extra efforts to survive. Due to globalization and changing trends women are now coming out for other professions too, but in this, they have to fulfill dual responsibilities of homemaker and working life while facing societal pressures. This study contributes to an understanding of the experiences of working women in a patriarchal, gendered, Muslim society. This study offers an indigenous conceptualization of contours, causes, consequences and coping strategies of work life balance among working women of a Public Sector Organization, through intersectional, multi-level, feminist approach, which give voice to working women. Women experiences are foregrounded in this study through individual level analysis, family systems, male dominated organization and contradiction of Islamic teachings with the societal norms regarding women's paid employment. Consequently, the Effort Recovery model was used for conceptualizing work life balance. Mixed method approach was used for data collection; quantitative data is collected through 10 questionnaire and then qualitative data is collected from the same respondents through semi-structured in-depth interviews from women of public sector organization based in Karachi, Pakistan. Findings of this study suggest that the culture of Pakistan is gendered in which women are usually left behind and does not provided with equal opportunity to vocalize their subjugated position in both family and work. Moreover, this study point out the facts that woman usually try hard to maintain their dual image of good women and ideal worker. This, of course, has implications for the intensity. This study further extends the used work life balance theoretical framework to include and consider it from the aspects of contours, causes, consequences and coping strategies for work life balance in the context of a public sector organization. However, the research also revealed that women in Pakistani public sector organization are not passive victims, but active agents, making context dependent constrained choices to prevent, cope or maintain work life balance. For policymakers, the findings suggest the need for the formulation of context-specific initiatives to address work-family issues in patriarchal Muslim societies.

Key Words: Work life balance, work life conflict, family interference, working women, Public sector organization.

1. Introduction

Work life balance (WLB) is becoming an important issue for both employee and employer. It is because of increased competition and frequent changes that has occurred in the business environment. Effective management of these changes is a key for success in competition. Work life balance is balanced condition in which there is less conflict between roles with satisfaction and sound functioning of oneself at home and work (Clark & Creswell, 2008). Work life balance is refers, state in which one juggle the daily pressure and stress. In this, multiple responsibilities regulated at professional and personal life. Work life balance restores through effective support at workplace. Research has proved it that employees who are balanced in their lives are more motivated and less stressed at work which ultimately increase the productivity and build sound workplace (Bedeian, Burke, & Moffett, 1988). Organizations in which there is work life balance, is more prefer by the employees as compared to others.

According to Shirley Chisholm (African American in US Congress), women has remained a victim of stereotyping and this all start from the time when doctor first says, it is a girl. Contextual meaning of his sentence are true for Pakistan, despite of the fact that Pakistan has the first women prime minister of the Islamic world. In a list published by TrustLaw (2011) for most dangerous countries of the world Pakistan stand at third. According to a research conducted by F. Ali (2013) 80% of women at workplace has experience sexual harassment and approximately 80% of housewives have experienced violence (Siddiqui, Hamid, & Siddiqui, 2000). Similarly, (Spencer & Chesler, 2007) state that almost 90% of Pakistani housewives have been sexually abused, beaten or struck at any point of time in their lives. According to Andersson et al. (2010) the figure of these research may be understated because reporting domestic violence is considered as a symbol of dishonor to the family and have serious consequences like divorce. In Pakistani society and in Islam divorce is highly discouraged (P. A. Ali & Gavino, 2008) but Islam also give the right to Muslim women to get divorce from her husband (Carroll, 1986). However, women in Pakistan do not prefer to exercise this right (Shaheed, 1986). As a matter of fact, the legal system of Pakistan is not a women friendly (Tazeen S Ali et al., 2011) and navigating this system can become very intimidating for women (Weiss, 2012). As a result, the lives of women can easily be steer by men (Chaudary, 2013).

This study provides a conceptualization of work life balance and guilt of not maintaining a balance between work life and personal life (Tazeen Saeed Ali, 2011; Chaudary, 2013; Hochschild, 1979). Empirical research has served as evidence that extreme form of oppression in women work life balance. Result from religion, culture and social category (Healy, Bradley, & Forson, 2011).

Number of feminist ideas served as a base of this study (Acker, 2011; Chaudary, 2013; Oakley, 1998) and according to an approach suggested by Layder (1993), work life balance of working women in Pakistani public Sector Organization can best be studied through intersectional perspective with multi-level feminist approach that help in studying the mechanism and structure that oppress working women. The approach of Layder (1993) suggests a framework that deal with micro, meso and macro levels of action. All layers of work life balance model suggested by this approach are interrelated but with different objective and approaches (Layder, 1993). Sirgy and Lee (2016) suggests that there are four factors that play a vital role in work life balance balanced role commitment, positive spillover, conflict of role and social alienation.

1.1.Problem Statement

Work life balance is an important aspect of our lives, maintaining work life balance in order to avoid work life conflict is of due importance. Therefore, “the aim of this Case study is to investigate work life balance experience through a feminist approach based on lived experiences. Furthermore, it also aims to examine intersectionality among various social structures and explain their influence on work life balance.”

1.2. Research Questions

The following research questions have guided this study:

- 01- What are the contours of work life balance experiences among women working of a public sector organization?
- 02- What are the reasons because of which working women of public sector organization are unable to manage their work life balance?
- 03- What are the consequences of not managing work life balance properly or work life imbalance?
- 04- What are different strategies through which working women of public sector organization deal with work life imbalance?

1.3. Scope

The scope of this study extends to only one Public Sector Organization of Pakistan. The name of the organization is kept confidential due to security reasons.

1.4. Assumptions

It is assumed that all of our participants have at least three year of experience and all of them have effaced work life balance need in their career.

1.5. Limitations

In fact, a research without a limitation is near to impossible. This study has also some predefined limitations;

- 01- This study has focused only one public sector organization
- 02- Resource limitation
- 03- Time limitation
- 04- Non response rate
- 05- Access limitation
- 06- Smaller population size
- 07- Respondents might share socially accepted answers
- 08- This study use narratives as display rather than as report on reality.

2. Literature Review

In this study, a context specific examination of work life balance is plan to be done for giving a contemporary and historical review of a working women situation in Pakistan. The principles of addressing broader economic and social context in examining inequalities are the base for this study (Healy et al., 2011; Syed & Özbilgin,

2009). This chapter aims to provide literature base for the study. It reviews working women of Pakistan from the context of history and cultural transformation.

2.1. Work Life Balance

Work life balance is a process through which one tries to manage a state of equilibrium between work and personal life (Jones, Burke, & Westman, 2013). Achieving this state of equilibrium is not an easy task and there is always a condition of push and pull between the responsibilities of family and work (Lockwood, 2003). Initially work life balance is considered as a responsibility of employee only but now it has taken the central responsibility in employment policies and practices (Kim, 2014). Due to globalization and market reterritorialization, in order to ensure work life balance a new concept of flexible work time is introduced through which employee performance can be enhanced (White, Hill, McGovern, Mills, & Smeaton, 2003). Similarly, in order to increase employee performance virtual offices are made by the employers to ensure work life balance of their employees (Hill, Hawkins, Ferris, & Weitzman, 2001).

2.2. Conceptualization of Work Life Balance

The study emphasize on the perspective of conflict between the roles of work and family (Potgieter & Barnard, 2010). This perspective includes work and family conflict and integration along with work life interference and balance (Oosthuizen & Mostert, 2010). The work over these perspectives was initially identified as a basic cause for work life balance problems (Roberts, 2007), which ultimately contribute to work family conflict (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985).

Initially the perspective of work life balance focused the negative impact of work on family (Greenhaus, Collins, & Shaw, 2003; Rost & Mostert, 2007) and it has more spill over affect from work family relationship rather than family work relationship (Frone, Russell, & Cooper, 1997; Fu & Shaffer, 2001). Therefore, the focus has shifted towards multidirectional interference between family and work (Oosthuizen & Mostert, 2010). Recently, work family relationship (complex) is studied with more in-depth analysis, with a tendency of using work home interference instead of work home balance, this balance suggests even distribution of home and work, which is not, always desired. In this study, work life balance is conceptualized from work home interference (Geurts et al., 2005), which is based on effort recovery theory of Meijman and Mulder (1998).

2.3. Work Home Interference

According to Geurts et al. (2005) work, home interference is a process in which behavior of an individual in one domain get influence by load reactions of other domain. Initially Geurts et al. (2005) has studied work home interference with a focus on negative relationship between work and home. Researchers have tested the assumptions that home might get influence from functions at work and work might get influence from the functions at home, and this influence is both positive and negative. According to Grzywacz and Marks (2000) there are four different but interrelated types of spillovers between home and work.

1. Negative spillover from work to home
2. Positive spillover from work to home
3. Negative spillover from home to work
4. Positive spillover from work to home

Furthermore, Geurts et al. (2005) characterize the interferences as four-dimensional construct that differentiate between direction of influence and quality of influence. Based on the work home interference there are four dimensions.

1. Negative work home interference, negative load reactions of work, affect functioning at home
2. Positive work home interference, positive load reactions of work, affect functioning at home
3. Negative home-work interference, negative load reactions of home, affect functioning at work
4. Positive home-work interference, positive load reactions of home, affect functioning at work.

Work home characteristics are base on role characteristics which ultimately affect behavior, strain or time involvement in one domain that are incompatible with the role in other domain. Greenhaus and Beutell (1985) have identified three type of work home conflict: time based, strain based and time base conflict. The effort recovery model better understands these interferences between home and work, which is a theoretical framework of this study.

2.4.Effort Recovery Model

It is a fundamental and most widely used model for work home interference (Meijman & Mulder, 1998). According to this model, there is a possible interference between private and work life, and these interferences affect the employee wellbeing (Geurts & Demerouti, 2003; Geurts et al., 2005; Mostert & Rathbone, 2007). According to the effort recovery model, effort expenditure is link with specific load reaction of individuals that further links with psycho-physiological reactions that are short term. These reactions include subjective, behavioral, and psychological responses like mood changing, change in energy level and hormones (Mostert & Oldfield, 2009; Van Tonder, 2005). According to Geurts and Demerouti (2003) the effort recovery model is all about quality and quantity of how recovery plays a vital role in one's life.

Effort recovery model is based on a central concept, work that require effort are link with creation of negative load effects, which spill over the domain of home. Therefore, it is difficult to recover at the domain of home from the efforts one has invested in the domain of work. This lack of recovery increase the chances that work demand potentially harm psychological health and leads to negative work home interference (Geurts & Demerouti, 2003). Frone et al. (1997) has linked the negative work home interference with depression, abuse, reduced wellbeing, or alcohol use. Positive home-work interference refers to positive influence created at home that affect good functioning at work. Whereas, positive work home interferences refers to the positive influence created at workplace that affect good functioning of an individual at home (Geurts et al., 2005; Oosthuizen & Mostert, 2010). According to the effort, recovery model work environment such as job autonomy, personal development may result in willingness of an individual ability to task and yield positive results (Geurts et al., 2005). Because of this, resources of one domain create a positive spillover on other domain and reduce the need for recovery, increase commitment and motivation, which may result in positive mobilization of energy (Bakker & Geurts, 2004).

According to Poelmans (2005) there are two type of recoveries in an individual, internal and external. Internal recovery occur during workdays and have the possibility that it might negatively affected by spillover of home demands. Whereas, external recovery occur after weekdays and have the possibility that it might negatively affect the spillover of work demands.

3. Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodology of this study along with the process of data collection and data analysis. This study uses a feminist point of view (lens) for examining the experiences of working women in Public sector organization.

3.1. Research Design

This study has used case study as a research strategy (Yin, 2009a) with mixed method approach (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). In this method, semi-structured interviews and surveys are used for data collection. For the purpose of exploring lived experiences of working women of a public sector organization of Pakistan, emphasis is given more on qualitative technique of data collection rather than quantitative. Previously a number of studies are conducted on work life balance and in all those studies an over emphasis is given to individual level analysis. So, the researchers has called for multi-level analysis of work life balance (Frone, 2003; Grzywacz, Carlson, Kacmar, & Wayne, 2007; Özbilgin, Beauregard, Tatli, & Bell, 2011; Parasuraman & Greenhaus, 2002; Poelmans, 2005). The mixed method approach use in this study has tries to address the call of researchers.

3.2. Mixed Method Approach

According to Casper, Eby, Bordeaux, Lockwood, and Lambert (2007), for data collection of work life balance surveys are mostly use in the studies between 1980 to 2003 and similarly, Shaffer, Joplin, and Hsu (2011), has also explored the same for the period of 1986 to 2010. But Fontana and Frey (2000), acknowledge the usage of qualitative studies for context specific studies. In Pakistan majority of the studies relating to work life balance use questionnaire (K. Ali & Hamid, 1999; Salam, 2014; Syed & Ali, 2013; Umer & Zia-ur-Rehman, 2013). Recently Mirza and Jabeen (2011), made an exception in their study. Researchers have called for mixed method studies in the field of work family relation (Eby, Casper, Lockwood, Bordeaux, & Brinley, 2005; Shaffer et al., 2011). Seale (2004), a feminist social researcher have encouraged using mixed method approach, while keeping in view the objective and context of the research. Similarly, Yin (2009b), have suggested to use multiple source of data collection for a case study.

Mixed method use in this research consisted of 10 questionnaire and 10 semi-structured interviews. Interviews of this research are conducted while focusing feminist research, whereas, background data of the participants is collected through questionnaire. According to Layder (2012), such mixed method research is a base for conducting multi layered research.

3.3. Instrument

- 3.71. Questionnaire – In mixed method research, initial study guide the second stage (Clark & Creswell, 2008). This study has adopted feminist approach for multi-level analysis of work family experience in the domain of under researched context and group. Initially data is collected from our participants through questionnaires after which semi-structured interview is conducted with our participants.
- 3.72. Semi-structured Interviews – In the field of social sciences, qualitative studies are believe to focus on exploring people behavior (Matthews & Ross, 2010; Silverman, 2011). For studying work-family relationship qualitative methods are preferred because of their ability to study context sensitive meanings of family and work domains (Özbilgin et al., 2011). Shaffer et al. (2011) have emphasized on the need for qualitative studies for work-family relationships and especially for under researched cultures. For the purpose of exploring subjective meanings and keeping non-hierarchal relationship between researcher and subject/participant feminist researcher, rely heavily on semi-structured

interviews (Oakley, 1981). This resembles with the research philosophy of critical realism (Ekstrom & Danermark, 2002) and with Layder (1993) research map, who is highly in favor of mixed method research for investigating social reality. In this study for deeper insight of the complexity of work life balance experience semi-structured interviews are used. The use of qualitative interviews aligns with research aims, theoretical framework, analytical framework, and philosophical assumptions.

3.4.Sampling

Researchers who study work-family relationship laid a great emphasis on giving proper justification for selection of sampling strategy (McDonald, Burton, & Chang, 2007). In qualitative sampling, for the purpose of data collection, non-probabilistic sampling has given a great importance, especially for purposeful sampling, self-selection, and snowball sampling technique (Chang, McDonald, & Burton, 2010). The culture of research in Pakistan is consider as infant (Pardhan, 2010). Native researchers who are undertaking researches in Pakistan are warned this culture (Mirza & Jabeen, 2011). In addition, even the management of organizations consider research as a waste of time (Ayub & Jehn, 2010). Therefore, in this study personal contacts were used for sampling which are in accordance with the culture and suggestions of other researchers. The selection of the organization is based on a recent event of 2017 when our selected public sector organization is acquired by State Bank of Pakistan from Ministry of Finance, Pakistan and within one year of acquisition number of women worker left the organization. Prior to conduct research a consent form was taken from the participant (for interview) and they will be given free time to study it and raise any questions if they want, further it is also allowed to them to skip any question and leave the interview at any time they want.

4. Data Analysis

This chapter divides into four sections, each answer one research question of the study.

4.1.Section No. 01 – Contours of work life balance

It empirically explains the multidimensionality of work life balance, specifically it explains the dual role of working women, they experience any conflict in it or not and what are the contours of work life balance that affect the balance of working women.

4.11.Profile – Out of 10 semi-structured interviews, six are from the participants that are from the age group of 26 to 25 years, two are from 26 to 45 years, one from 46 to 55 and one greater than 55 years of age. All of the participants were Muslim (sect not inquired) and either married, divorced or widow. From our participants six have a higher education of MBA/ MPhil and all other have a maximum education of Bachelor's Degree (02 or 04 Years). On average they have a 6 to 10 years of experience, in terms of employment status seven are permanent and three are contractual and on average they have the income of PKR 70,000/-.

4.12.Ideal worker and good women – based on empirical analysis this study suggests that not maintaining work life balance is a base for work family conflict, it is a dichotomy of women guilt and structural pressures linked with the inability to simultaneously perform dual roles and achieve a status of ideal worker and good women.

According to Acker (2011) ideal worker is usually refers to as, “he” and believed to be one who work long hours and remain unaffected from domestic responsibilities. In view of Hochschild (1997) ideal worker is one, whose performance on paid employment remain unaffected from family specific

responsibilities. Whereas, a good women in the context of Pakistan is one who fulfill the responsibilities of home and provide additional income when needed, from paid job or from household savings. In addition to this, she must remain in veil and do not express her emotions or ideas, remain calm, tolerant, unselfish, and compromising (S. M. Ali & ul Haq, 2006; Tazeen Saeed Ali, 2011). Women try to fulfill this dual image/ responsibility, inability to fulfillment is link with personal deficiency or irresponsibility.

4.13. Emotional labor – according to Sabhlok (2005), in Muslim societies the honor of man only associates to him but the honor of women extends to whole family and even to region. Out of our all participants no one has expressed any doubt about men character when they work outside and with female colleagues but a number of women, especially who were single have explained that they usually struggle hard to protect their honor from males at workplace. Similarly, they have explained that they usually experience contextual emotional labor. One of the participants explained that;

“In Karachi, taxi or rickshaw driver never seems surprised when they see women alone. However, the moment women take it alone his perception change and he thinks you are going on date. And if you come late at night this view become even more negative.”

4.14. Contours of work life balance – most of the working women see maintenance of work life balance as their primary responsibility and consider it very important to maintain the status of good women and ideal worker. In this section, contours of work life balance are explained by revising the concept of prevalence. Prevalence means occurrence of something or commonness of something at any specific moment. The term contours is associated with the geology of earth and use in sculpting. Usage of this term in study allows adaptation of wave and textures of work life balance.

4.15. Directions of work life imbalance – all of our participants who are married agree on the point that experiencing work life imbalance or work family conflict is very common and if one is on the point that she has not experienced it, she was being dishonest. As explained by one of our participant;

“I am one person but dealing with two sides, at one side there is my family and on the other side, there is my work. Off course if there is any issue on one side, it will affect the other and similarly if I'm relaxed from one side it also affects the other side.”

4.16. Types of work life imbalance – work life imbalance give rise to work family conflict so in the study they are used interchangeably. There are four types of work life imbalance that are time based, behavior based, strain based, and psychological based work life imbalance. From empirical point of view, there are five additional type of work life imbalance that are gender based, marriage based, class based, socio cultural based, and symbolic work life imbalance. It is a general belief that single women experience less work life imbalance as compared to women. As explained by one of our participant,

“No doubt single women experience less work life imbalance because they do not have to think and manage their in laws.”

4.17. Intensity of work life imbalance – some of our participants become aggressive when they talked about male domination and the modification of Islamic teachings in the society of Pakistan. Even those who have made their position after great hard work gave us the feeling of powerlessness. Most of the women have attempted, to make sense of their position, across dual role of breadwinner and homemaker. Some of the participants accepted that at some point of time in their lives they think to just give up, as explained by one of our participant,

“In my life their occasionally come such points where I think to give up... I cannot fulfill these dual responsibilities anymore.”

4.18. Frequency of work life imbalance – as per findings, not everyone (women) observed the same intensity of work life imbalance and it fluctuates with context. Its intensity usually increase because of repetition, thus different dimensions of work life imbalance must be interlink and examine collectively

to understand the contours of work life imbalance. According to majority of our participants, they experience work life imbalance on daily basis. This is true especially for those who are breadwinner, newlyweds, or a mother of infant. As shared by one of our participant,

“There was a marriage of my brother in law and at the same time new project was going on in the organization because of which I had to stay late and when I reach home everyone at home says she is a workaholic lady. Moreover, if I try to leave early from office everyone at office says yes off course she is a house women.”

In western societies, it is not an obligation over working women to go to the wedding ceremony of their in-laws and this is acceptable over there but for Pakistan, it is obligatory for working women to go to such event if in any case they fail to go it results in long lasting tensions.

4.19. Duration of work life imbalance – most of our participants are of view that work life imbalance is a base for work family conflict and it is natural component of women’s life and few says they had no other choice. As explained by one of our participants,

“I agree my life is tough, very tough. I usually encounter the situation when I’ am at office and my children’s are waiting back home, hungry. This is how it is. I have to manage this and I have been doing it, and now it seems that I’ am becoming use to it and so do my family.”

4.2. Section No. 02: Causes of work life imbalance

In this study we have classified the causes of work life imbalance into three domains work specific, family specific, and domain unspecific.

4.21. Work specific – it is one of the major reason because of which female workers fail to maintain work life balance. In most of the organizations especially in public sector organization, it is a general belief that higher positions are for men and women are usually not allow to go beyond certain limit in terms of promotion. As narrated by one of our participant,

“When I came in this organization I worked very hard but after 02 years I realized that management doesn’t want to see me on higher position because they always reward male employees. After a while I also left trying and started to enjoy my life like typical public sector organization.”

The above mention narration clears that in public sector organization women fail to maintain balance between work and family. In public sector organization, they give more importance and time to family as compared to work as a result organization face a loss of productivity.

4.21.1. Limited flexibility – flexible working hours are becoming very common round the globe but in Pakistan, no such flexibility is given to employees regardless of the sector and organization. The only type of flexible working for the employees in Pakistan is one in which colleagues become backup of one another. However, this flexible working is with some challenges like quality of work and obligatory unpaid workload.

Our select public sector organization has very long working hours from 08:00 AM to 05:30 PM and if any employee is coming late even at 08:01 AM they are marked late. Male dominated organizations are usually link with pressure and long working hour’s (Johns, 2010), because it is the part of their evaluation criteria. According to Asghar, Wahid, Khalid, and Zaheer (2009), it is normally stereotyped that women of Pakistan refuse to work late hours and when they try to do so it affect their mental and physical health (Shakil Ahmad, Fakhr, & Ahmed, 2011). As narrated by one of our participant,

“In my organization there is a culture that if you are sitting late night than you have a lot of work and if you finish your work early it is believed that you don’t have any work. So most of the people in organization spend their day in gossips and start their work after 12:00 PM so they can sit late.”

The above mention narration clearly narrates the importance and culture of late sitting in the organization, which affect the work life balance.

- 4.21.2. Inadequate childcare support – from the empirical data collected through questionnaire, most of our participants have shown a serious concern about unavailability of childcare facility at workplace. Similarly, childcare facility is considered as a serious cause of work family tensions. Majority of the Pakistani working women favor childcare facility but only in theory, they do not practice it because of poor service, security, terrorism and distance from home. In Pakistan, most of the couples live in joint family system because of which they have more trust on their family members for childcare as compared to some external person. As a serious concern one of our participant shared,

“I don’t trust childcare centers regardless of the place they exist because child of my sister in law got kidnapped from one of the childcare center facility. So, I prefer to leave my child at home with my mother in law.”

Because of inadequate childcare support, women naturally give more attention to their family and less to their work, which ultimately leads to work life imbalance.

- 4.22. Family specific – in Pakistan, domestic labor is always gender, regardless of the fact that labor market of Pakistan has undergone through a number of changes, familial and societal habitus have no changed with same pace/ moment. As a result, still when women of middle or lower class family leave their home for job, their honor is always question. Similarly, it is not consider right and socially acceptable if men share the responsibilities of housework. As narrated by one of our participants,

“In Pakistan, it is not norm and usually people consider it odd if they found any men doing household stuffs. They usually say (especially own family members), this is not right/ proper or you are trying to go against nature. Here it is very common to change the religion and present it in a shape that is beneficial for oneself and usually nobody dares to question it.”

Due to family habitus, caring and responsibilities most of the working women put extra efforts, they usually neglect their work and care for families, which affect their performance and lead to work life imbalance.

- 4.23. Domain unspecific – women professional and social disadvantages are back by the evidences of the research, which are because of personal habits and structural barriers. Results of the questionnaire show that half of our participants agree that they are on less advantageous position compared to men. However, for this study they are not agent or victim. Furthermore, according to empirical evidence, women construct and reconstruct their identities as good women and ideal worker that show their identity is not static.

The work of Shaheen (2003) and Bruck and Allen (2003), explains the role of personality traits in the context of work family experience. According to them, most important women habitus were their aspirations to become good women (Samih, 2009), and as per societal definition, they must turn house into home. Most of our participants are of view that men should also participate in household works. But on the other hand there is also an illusion of two spheres which belief a sexes are vastly different, women primary role is “home making.”

4.3. Section No. 03: Consequences of not managing work life balance

Work life imbalance leads to work family conflict, in this section consequence of work life imbalance are explain in three domains work specific, family specific and unspecified domain (Bellavia, 2005).

4.31. Work specific

4.31.1. Slow growth – according to Hofstede (1984), cultural dimensions Pakistan is a high power distance country where women are usually associated to some predefined positions and professions. Expectations of women about growth and promotion vary a lot and slow growth of women is mostly because of work life imbalance. Women at workplace face discrimination in terms of reward based on gender and to some extent women themselves have also internalized and accepted it. Because of domestic responsibilities there are certain jobs which are consider friendly for women and they usually favor these jobs (Samih, 2009). One of the participant shared,

“As women in this organization it is better that you live out of fool’s paradise. There is no promotion for women here just because of our marriage and children’s. Because we have dual responsibilities, management thinks we are incapable of working like men. So they usually do not give us hard task at first which provide us relaxation but this also upsets our reward and promotion.”

4.31.2. Job discontinuity – according to the concept of good women, she is one who provides additional income when needed, which means they should only work when there is a need and if there is no need she should discontinue her job and give her full time to her family. All of our participants majority of them said it clearly that their family is more important as compared to work/ job and if they had to chose between job and family they will without any doubt select family. Most of our participants explained that before marriage they have left very good opportunities because they have the fear, there in laws will not allow them to work after marriage. Similarly, another women explained that her very good and talented friend have left the job because after marriage she is forced to do so.

Most of the women work after marriage even after facing serious objections from relatives because their life partners do not have a stable job. As explained by one of our participant,

“Before marriage I have a plan to leave this job but after marriage I have cancelled my plan because my husband does not have a stable job and he also allowed me to do so. Our most of the relatives are against our decision but we both are facing it. My husband always says you will leave this job once I will get a good and stable job.”

4.31.3. Reduced job performance – in labor market, the competency of women usually drops when they have children and most of the women comply with such stereotypes by giving less productivity as a choice to deal with work life imbalance or work life conflict (Fothergill & Feltey, 2003). As previously discussed, for most of our participant’s family is more important and because of it they give less attention to work, it ultimately reduce their performance. Similarly, if any worker is coming at 08:01 AM her/his performance and punctuality is questioned but if the same employee stays and work until 10:00 PM no one bother to appreciate.

4.32. Family Specific

All of our participants agreed that being a good mother is more important than being a good worker, and they only work because they want to support their family financially. In this, they are usually unable to fulfill some rights of their children’s and family.

4.32.1. Family negligence – the family specific consequences of work life imbalance for single women are different from those of married or divorced. For single women consequences only extend to their family and siblings but for married women it extends to their children, husband, in laws and family (parents). As explained, *“when you are at job slowly an gradually your family keeps on going far away from you and in work you usually do not notice it.”*

4.32.2. Mother Child relation – in the culture of Pakistan, institution of mother is strongly embedded. All our participants agreed that their job affect their marital performance. All of them also agreed that regardless of their professional role, women make a lot sacrifice in their lives. One of our old participant shared that,

“Previously mobile phones were not allowed in this organization. One day I came to office and my son was alone at home while paying with friends he fall and injured himself. After five hours when I reached home than I came to know about the event that day I scolded myself and my career.”

According to our participant, this event is occurred because of her paid job and in one way or other. She has neglected her primary responsibility of childcare.

4.32.3. Delayed marriage – it is one of the most important family related consequence of work life imbalance. Working women usually experience delayed marriages because of their role interference between home maker and paid employment. Women who works are usually consider as independent and bold. So, most of the family either make a condition that she will not continue her job after marriage or simply reject her because they want less bold and independent girl for their boy.

4.32.4. Marital conflict – according to habitus of women, there is a great importance of marital status in Pakistan. As they are someone’s daughter or sister and most of them depend on their parents to select their life partner. Therefore, there is usually very little time for understanding. According to Hussain (1999), in Islam there is no foundation that support arrange marriage, but Muslims are encouraged to remain optimistic and grateful to Allah. This can explain the difficulty that one woman might experience in her marriage. And if after marriage they fail to maintain work life balance it result in serious marital conflict. Similar situation is explained by one of our participant,

“I was married to a person to whom I have never seen in my life. Before marriage, they were in favor of my job but after 02 to 03 months our marital conflict started and from time to time they kept on increasing. At the end he left me at my home and now its 02 years he has not returned to take me back.”

4.33.Domain unspecific

In west, consumption of alcohol and drug usage is considered as health related issues resulting from work life imbalance. However, in this study no such case was identified.

4.33.1. Health related issues – both male and female are equally affected by work life imbalance. As narrated by one of our participant,

“In 2006 there was a project when new machinery was coming, everyone has to stay late they don’t care about anyone’s health, during these day one of our worker got heart attack but only thing that matter to organization is completion of project.”

Long extensive hours of work can result in serious health related issues especially problems related to backbone, stress, strain etc. As explained,

“Every day I think I should quit because I was left with no energy at end of the day, and most of the time my stress cause problem in my family.”

4.4.Section No. 04: Strategies for maintaining work life balance

In this section, coping strategies for dealing with work life imbalance or for maintain work life balance were explained from the domain perspective of work, family, and unspecified domain.

4.41.Work related

4.41.1. Foregoing opportunities – as slow growth is one of the most prominent cause of work life imbalance, on the same time women consciously leave the opportunity for training and promotion because of their family. This regards as one of the strategy to reduce conflict between family and work. One of our participant shared,

“Most of the women prefer to work in human resource or accounts department. They don’t prefer to work in production because they want to go early, although as per my believe there are more chances for growth and one can go on time in production.”

In the above narration, women have associated few departments with shorter working hours and they prefer to work in these. Similarly, they also associate few departments with opportunity for promotion. Most of the women prefer to work shorter and want to give more time to their family, so promotions doesn’t matter to them.

4.41.2. Organizational policies – there are also some organizational benefits that are available to women which help them in coping with work family tension and maintain work life balance. In our selected public sector organization, there are four types of leaves available, which help women to maintain work life balance. There are maternal leaves of 45 days, annual leaves of 30 days, 10 casual and sick leaves. Beside this if, someone is going for Hajj or Umrah, they are given extra leaves. In our selected organization, there is a concept of late coming and early going, which are allowed to employees three times a month. According to one participant,

“In terms of leaves this organization is good, it allows us to accumulate our leaves and then en-cash or utilize them any time.”

4.42. Family related

4.42.1. Help from other family members – in joint family systems of Pakistan it is very common that if one is going on work other members of family will take care of their children. As explained,

“Before marriage I was totally against join family system but after marriage my view changed completely because as compared to any other colleague at works I’ am very relaxed from my children side.”

Working women use this as a strategy to maintain work life balance.

4.42.2. Hiring maid – another strategy used by working women to maintain work life balance is hiring maid for domestic works. As explained,

“I found it very difficult to work in office and home. Therefore, I have hired a maid for domestic works. Beside office days, she also come on Saturday and does laundry. I supervise in her work. The only day I work is Sunday when I cook food for my family.”

4.42.3. Sacrificing Self – it is the most significant coping strategy used by working women to maintain work life balance, sacrificing self. This strategy is based on socio-cultural context. Most of the women sacrifice and compromise to become good women, even this is done by housewives. As explained by one of our participant,

“There are very limited job opportunities available for women. So, one must sacrifice self and take up every possible opportunity available to them for growth and development.”

4.43. Domain unspecific

4.43.1. Managing time – our select public selected organization does not allow part time work, as like most of the organizations of Pakistan. Because of this, many women are force to leave their jobs as they fail to maintain work life balance. One of our participant shared,

“It is very hard for me to perform double duties and soon I might also leave this job.”

Another best option available to working women for managing their work life balance is managing their time properly and effectively. One woman shared,

“I make favorite food for my family on weekends, do laundry; press cloths give time to my children and attend events if there are any. I love to do these all works daily but all is only possible on weekends and I’ am glad I manage it.”

5. Conclusion

This study has focused the lives of working women from a public sector organization of Pakistan. This study has answered its four research questions

In this study, work family relationship for working women of a public sector organization are studied with theoretical perspective of effort recovery model and Bourdieus concept. This study has also explained that if a woman fails to manage work life balance it is link with her failure to fulfill responsibility. In addition, when women go out of home to work their integrity and honor is usually question. The dichotomy of work life balance is link with pressure and guilt associated with her inability to collectively achieve the status of good women and ideal worker (Acker, 2011; Tazeen S Ali et al., 2011; Chaudary, 2013; Hochschild, 1989; Lewis & Humbert, 2010). Married working women try hard to save their marriages by sacrificing themselves. For contours, this study has combined a number of aspects from the aspect of work, family, and unspecified domain. Similarly, these contexts were used for causes, consequences and coping strategies. In Pakistan, many people mold the teachings of Islam as per their demand and need, but only for middle and lower families. For high or upper class family, it is not a big thing to go out and work. In addition, long working hours are also a major reason because of which many working women get frustrated as they are unable to fulfill their dual responsibility of work and family.

There are also some stereotypes about working of men, that if men help in domestic work it is not good or right but if a women go out and work it is acceptable. Working women are usually unable to give proper time to their family and in laws because of which a number of family conflict start which have serious consequences and even go to the extent of divorce. Similarly, women are found disappointed because they think they are inferior to men in terms of work, productivity and social status. Improper management of emotions affects everyone but women are more disadvantaged as compared to men because of their gender.

Working women adopt a number of strategies to maintain work life balance or to deal with work life imbalance like giving up the desire to grow (growth and development), using organizational policies effectively, seeking help from other family members, hiring maid for work, sacrificing their selves and managing their time efficiently.

5.1. Implication of study

The implications of this study are as follow;

- 01- One can better understand work life balance from the perspective of women working in public sector organization.
- 02- The causes, consequences, and coping strategies to deal with work life imbalance can better be understood through this research in detail.
- 03- This research can be used for policy making to stop the lost of talented women labor force.

5.2. Future research

As this study is done on a smaller scale with limited resources, therefore its results cannot be generalized. This study has focused only one organization it is therefore strongly recommended to conduct a study with multiple organizations on larger scale. Furthermore, a cross-national study is also recommended for the same to better understand work life balance of working women.

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